

Karyological Investigations on Four Species of Dung Beetles (Insecta)

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Ashish Rathore

Research Scholar
Department Of Zoology
PM College Of Excellence Govt Arts And
Science College
Ratlam, Madhya Pradesh, India,

B.S. Kirade

Assistant Professor
Department Of Zoology
Govt. P.G. College, Jaora
Ratlam, Madhya Pradesh, India

Milind Dange

Professor
Department Of Zoology
PM College of Excellence, Govt Arts and
Science College
Ratlam, Madhya Pradesh, India

Abstract	Karyological investigations were carried out on adult male individuals of <i>Geotrupes stercorarius</i> L., <i>Aphodius antaques</i> Fabr, <i>A. calaphadius</i> Reitter, and <i>A. crenatus</i> Har. belonging to families Geotrupidae and Scarabaeidae. <i>G. stercorarius</i> L. possesses $2n = 22 : 10 + Xy_p$, whereas <i>A. antaques</i> Fabr, <i>A. calaphadius</i> Reitter and <i>A. crenatus</i> Har. Possesses $2n = 20 : 9+ Xy_p$ sex mechanism. We have discussed and described meiosis and mitosis.
Keywords	Coleoptera, Geotrupidae, Scarabaeidae, Karyotype, Autosome, Sex-chromosome mechanism.
Introduction	<p>Superfamily scarabaeoidea is one of the most distinct sections of the Coleoptera. Many modern authors recognize a considerable number of families but the adopted classification is conservative. It comprises about 6 families. Beetles of family Geotrupidae are also called 'dor beetles' they are large convex and mostly of coprophilous habits. It constructs burrows about 18 inches deep in the earth, below a patch of dung, and portion of the latter are carried down to serve as food for the larvae. Each burrow is filled at its blind end with a plug of dung in which a single egg is deposited (Richards & Davies, 1957).</p> <p>Scarabaeidae is very large family of more or less convex insects. It is a largest family of Coleoptera comprising 30,000 species and 600 genera and include above 91% of all Scarabaeoid species worldwide (Fincher, 1981). Adults and larvae of a few species of scarabs are economically important and may cause considerable damage due to defoliation or root-feeding. Scarabaeidae can be divided into two major divisions i.e. Laprosticti and Pleurosticti (Erichson, 1848). The Aphodiinae and Scarabaeinae include approximately 6,850 species worldwide (about 22% of scarabaeoids and 25% of Scarabaeidae). They can be herbivores, fungivores, coprophagus, necrophagus, saprophagus and some time carnivores. The group includes an intriguing array of life histories, and many interesting adaptations. Many scarabs are beneficial because they pollinate plants, recycle plant material, and are valuable dung recyclers. During present investigation, the chromosomes of four species belonging to two genera were undertaken.</p>
Objective of study	The aim of the present study is to investigate the karyological characteristics (chromosome number, morphology, and sex-chromosome mechanism) of four species of dung beetles - <i>Geotrupes stercorarius</i> L, <i>Aphodius antaques</i> Fabr, <i>A. calaphadius</i> Reitter, and <i>A. crenatus</i> Har. The research focuses on analyzing mitotic and meiotic stages to understand interspecific chromosomal variations and contribute to the cytotaxonomic classification of the families Geotrupidae and Scarabaeidae.
Review of Literature	The families Geotrupidae and Scarabaeidae, under the superfamily Scarabaeoidea, have been widely studied cytogenetically due to their ecological and economic importance. Earlier studies by Smith & Virkki (1978), Yadav (1983, 1989), and Dange (1991) highlighted chromosomal diversity in Coleoptera. Rathore (2010) reported karyotypic variations in several scarabaeoid beetles from central India. The $2n = 20 + Xy_p$ sex-chromosome mechanism is considered primitive and common in Scarabaeidae. However, cytogenetic data on many Aphodius species remain limited, justifying further investigation. High-quality chromosome-level genome assemblies have transformed insect cytogenetics, showing that chromosome fusions and fissions drive karyotype evolution via conserved breakpoints and interstitial telomeres (Lukhtanov & Pazhenkova, 2025).
Methodology	Adult male individuals of four species belonging to four genera <i>Geotrupes stercorarius</i> L., <i>Aphodius antaques</i> Fabr, <i>A. calaphadius</i> Reitter and <i>A. crenatus</i> Har. constitute the material for present investigation. All the beetles were collected under the mercury vapour lamps during October to December 2023- 2024 from Ratlam and Mandsaur (Madhya Pradesh). Chromosome preparations were made following Yadav and Lyapunova (1983).

Result and Discussion

Geotrupes stercorarius L The diploid number of 22 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig. 1)

The karyotype is composed of nine pairs of autosomes and X and y sex chromosomes (Fig. 2).

Autosome pair 1-6 were metacentric, pair 7 is acrocentric and pair 8 and 9 were submetacentric, the X chromosome was submetacentric and y being the small dot like chromosome. When arranged according to size the autosomes show a gradual decrease. The chromatids appear closely applied to one another throughout their lengths. Metaphase I possess ten rod shaped autosomal bivalents and sex bivalents Xy_p (fig.9).

During prometaphase chromosome depicted chromosome fibrils.

As a result of the first meiotic division being reductional two types of metaphase II plates were formed one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig.10).

The male chromosomal formula is $10AA + Xy_p$.

Aphodius antaques Fabricius The diploid number of 20 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig.03). The karyotype is composed of nine pairs of autosomes and X and y chromosomes (Fig.04). Autosome pairs 1-5, 7 and 8 are metacentric and autosome pairs 6 and 9 were submetacentric where as pair 9 along X chromosomes was acrocentric, the y chromosome is small and dot like. Metaphase I possess nine rods or dumb-bells shaped autosomal bivalents and sex bivalent Xy_p . (Fig. 11).

As a result of the first meiotic division being reductional two types of metaphase II plates were formed one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig. 12).

The male chromosomal formula is $9AA + Xy_p$.

Aphodius calaphadius Reitter The diploid number of 20 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig. 05).

The karyotype is composed of nine pairs of autosomes and X and y chromosomes (Fig. 6).

Autosome pair 1, 2, 4 and 7 were metacentric and pairs 5,6 and 8 were submetacentric, pairs 3 and 9 were acrocentric, X and y chromosome were metacentric. When arranged according to size the autosomes show a gradual decrease. The chromatids appear closely applied to one another throughout their lengths. Metaphase I possess nine rod shaped autosomal bivalents and sex bivalents Xy_p . (Fig.13).

As a result of the first meiotic division being reductional two types of metaphase II plates were formed one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig. 14).

The male chromosomal formula is $9AA + Xy_p$.

Aphodius crenatus Har. The diploid number of 20 chromosomes was revealed at the spermatogonial metaphase (Fig. 07).

The karyotype comprises nine pairs of autosomes and X and y chromosomes (Fig. 08); pairs 1-5 were metacentric, pair 6-9 were submetacentric and X chromosome is submetacentric while y chromosome was acrocentric. Nine rod shaped autosomal bivalents and the Xy_p constituted the metaphase I plate (Fig. 15).

As a result of the first meiotic division being reductional two types of metaphase II plates were formed one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig. 16) together with nine autosomes.

The male chromosomal formula is $9AA+Xy_p$.

The family Scarabaeidae known cytologically by 369 species belonging to 146 genera and 18 subfamilies (Yadav 1983, 1989, Dange 1991, Dange et al. 2013, Rathore, 2010). The sex determination mechanism $2n=20+Xy_p$ considered primitive in the family Scarabaeidae and for the order Coleoptera (Smith and Virkki, 1978). Among the autosomes, long heterochromatic chromosome arms are shown by *A. antaques* Fabr while *A. calaphadius* Reitter and *A. crenatus* Har show short arms which are heterochromatic. This character is unusual in Aphodius species studied by (Wilson, 2002). The karyotypes of all the species are distinctive, and this is a consistent feature of the Aphodius species studied. Karyotype differences have led to the recognition of separate, sometimes new, species, whose existence had been unsuspected. Notable examples are *A. fimetarius* (L.) and *A. pedellus* (DeGeer) (Wilson, 2001) and *A. niger* Illiger and *A. wilsonae* Maté & Angus (Maté, Angus, 2005). In both cases DNA differences support the conclusions drawn from the karyotypes (Maté, 2003). In the present investigations the total chromosome length was found to be maximum in *Aphodius antaques* Fabr (69.09µ) and minimum in *A. calaphadius* Reitter (58.23µ). All chromosomes show a gradual decrease in size. The size of X chromosome smallest in *Geotrupes stercorarius* L. (2.22µ) and largest in *A. crenatus* Har (2.92µ). *Geotrupes stercorarius* L. has the largest y (2.26µ) whereas y was smallest in *A. calaphadius* Reitter (2.08µ).

Comparative studies of the karyotypes of beetles are presented in table 1.

Table 1 : Karyotype analysis of one species of *Geotrupes* and three species of *Aphodius* spp.

Sr. No.	Species	Chromosome pairs in percentage length										Length in µ				
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	X	y	TCL	X	y
1	<i>Geotrupes stercorarius</i> L.	13.39	13.21	13.14	11.89	11.76	11.66	11.35	11.02	9.86	9.46	4.43	2.52	58.37	2.22	2.26
2	<i>Aphodius antaques</i> Fabr	25.85	19.84	17.18	15.83	12.77	12.38	12.33	12.14	9.86	-	4.92	4.18	69.09	2.46	2.09
3	<i>A. calaphadius</i> Reitter	17.19	14.27	14.12	12.62	12.49	11.63	11.50	11.10	11.59	-	5.50	4.16	58.23	2.75	2.08
4	<i>A. crenatus</i> Har	16.80	15.40	14.50	14.20	13.20	12.90	12.20	11.60	11.40	-	5.83	4.48	61.10	2.92	2.24

TCL = Total chromosome length.

Conclusion

The karyological analysis of four dung beetle species revealed differences in chromosome number, morphology, and sex-chromosome systems. *Geotrupes stercorarius* showed $2n = 22$, while *Aphodius* species had $2n = 20$ with Xy_p mechanism. Distinct karyotypic features support their taxonomic distinction and highlight the significance of cytogenetics in beetle classification.

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